

testers were crossed with Xiu-Shui 117 and T8340, F₁ spikelet fertility was higher with Xu-Shui 117 than with T8340. Fertility differed up to 39.6%

between Xu-Shui 117/indica and T8340/indica. Indica/japonica F₁ fertility may be high in certain crosses. Some varieties produce fertile F₁ plants

with both indica and japonica types. Such wide compatibility could be used to exploit indica-japonica heterosis. □

Maintainers and restorers for different cytoplasmic male sterility systems

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In a hybrid rice breeding program based on cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) and a fertility restoration system, diverse CMS sources are essential to preventing disease or insect epidemics caused by genetic association between disease or insect susceptibility and the cytoplasmic factors inducing male sterility. IIRRI has six CMS sources: 'wild rice abortive pollen' (cms-WA), cms-bo or BT, cms-TN, Gambiaca (cms-Gam), *Oryza rufipogon* (cms-rfp), and *Oryza sativa f. spontanea* (cms-sp). To use them in hybrid rice breeding, maintainers and restorers among available elite lines must be identified for each system.

A large number of restorers and maintainers have been identified in China and at IIRRI for the most widely used cms-WA system. To identify effective maintainers and restorers for other CMS systems, we crossed a number of indica, japonica, and indica/japonica derivative lines developed in Korea with six CMS lines derived from different cytotesterility sources.

The F₁s were evaluated for spikelet fertility during 1986 dry season at IIRRI, to determine whether the male parent was a restorer (spikelet fertility >80%), partial restorer (spikelet fertility 30-79%), partial maintainer (spikelet fertility 1-29%), or maintainer (spikelet fertility 0-1%).

Lines Suweon 222, Suweon 303, Suweon 304, Suweon 305, Cheolweon 21, Cheolweon 29, Bokgwangbyeon, Jibu 2, Jinheung, and Nongbong maintained almost all sources of CMS used (see table). However, restorers were identified only for cms-WA and cms-Gam systems. The cms-Gam source

Fertility restoration by some elite lines or varieties in testcrosses with 6 CMS lines derived from different sources. ^a IIRRI, 1989.

Genotype	Wu 10 A (cms-boro)	P 203 A (cms-TN)	IR46828 A (cms-WA)	YAZ A (cms-Gam)	MS 577 A (cms-sp)	Reimei A (cms-rfp)
Suweon 287	—	PR	PM	—	M	M
Suweon 288	—	M-PR	R	R	M	M
Suweon 264	—	M-PM	R	R	M	M
Suweon 304	M	PR	M	M	—	M
Suweon 303	M	PM	M	M	M	M
Suweon 305	—	M	M	M	M	M
Suweon 318	—	PR	—	—	—	PM-PR
Suweon 319	—	—	R	R	—	—
Suweon 306	—	PM	—	M	—	—
Suweon 325	—	PM	PM-R	R	—	M
Suweon 326	—	M	—	—	—	—
Suweon 329	—	—	—	R	—	M
Suweon 222	M	M-PM	M	M	M	M
Milyang 63	—	PM	—	PR	—	—
Milyang 68	—	PR	PM	R	M	M
Milyang 46	—	PM-PR	—	—	—	—
Milyang 30	—	—	R	R	M	PM
Milyang 54	—	PM-PR	R	—	—	PM
Milyang 75	M	PM	—	M	—	M
Iri 344	—	—	PR-R	R	M	M
Iri 360	—	—	R	R	—	M
Iri 361	—	PR	—	—	—	—
Iri 364	—	—	M	M	—	M
Iri 366	—	PM	M	M	—	—
Cheolweon 21	M	PM	M	M	M	M
Cheolweon 29	M	PM	M	M	M	M
Jibu 1	M	—	—	—	—	M
Jibu 2	M	PR	M	M	—	M
Bokgwangbyeon	M	PM	M	M	M	—
Bonggwangbyeon	—	—	—	M	—	—
Nongbaeg	M	—	M	M	—	M
Jinheung	M	PM	M	M	M	M
Pungok	—	—	—	M	M	M
Daechangbyeon	—	—	—	M	M	—
IR46828B	PR	PM	M	PR	PM	M
IR46831B	—	PM	M	PR	PM	M
IR48483B	PM-PR	—	M	PR	M	M

^aR = restorer, PR = partial restorer, PM = partial maintainer, M = maintainer.

was relatively easier to restore than the cms-WA source because some maintainers of cms-WA (IR46828B, IR46831B, IR48483B) were partial restorers of cms-Gam and some partial maintainers or partial restorers of cms-WA (Suweon 325, Milyang 68, Iri 344) were restorers of cms-Gam.

The cms-TN source was developed at IIRRI in the genetic background of traditional rice cultivar Pankhari 203. But the tall, photoperiod-sensitive P 203 line

cannot be used to develop high-yielding F₁ rice hybrids with improved plant type.

Earlier attempts to identify effective maintainers among elite lines have been unsuccessful. This study identified Suweon 326 as an effective maintainer. Through recurrent backcrossing, we are attempting to develop a new CMS line possessing cms-TN cytoplasm and the nuclear genotype of Suweon 326. □